

Project acronym: CS3MESH4EOSC

Deliverable D4.4

Full validation of application and use-cases for all workflows

Contractual delivery date	30-06-2023 (M36)
Actual delivery date	13-10-2023
Grant Agreement no.	863353
Work Package	WP4
Nature of Deliverable	D (Demo)
Dissemination Level	PU (Public)
Lead Partner	PSNC
Document ID	CS3MESH4EOSC-22-026
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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 863353

Versioning and Contributions History

<i>Version</i>	<i>Date</i>	<i>Authors</i>	<i>Notes</i>
0.1	18.09.2023	Maciej Brzeźniak (PSNC)	Initial draft
0.2	25.09.2023	Maciej Brzeźniak (PSNC)	Early draft
0.3	05.10.2023	Maciej Brzeźniak (PSNC)	Complete document for partners and STC review
0.4	09.10.2023	Juri Höbelbarth (University of Münster)	Revised Open Data Systems part
0.5	09.10.2023	Ron Trompert (SURF)	Revised Data Transfers part
0.6	09.10.2023	Marcin Sieprawski (Ailleron)	Reviewed the deliverable
0.7	09.10.2023	Holger Angenent (University of Münster)	Reviewed the deliverable
0.8	09.10.2023	Maciej Brzeźniak (PSNC)	Edits of pictures etc.
0.9	09.10.2023	Maciej Brzeźniak (PSNC)	Review
1.0	09.10.2023	Maciej Brzeźniak (PSNC)	Final version
1.1	11.10.2023	Sonia Mentrída (CERN)	Formatting

Table of Contents

<i>Versioning and Contributions History</i>	2
<i>Table of Figures</i>	3
<i>1 Introduction</i>	4
<i>2 Full validation of the use-cases for all workflows</i>	5
2.1 Portability considerations	5
2.2 Portability validation.....	6
2.3.1 Data Science Environments	6
2.3.2 Open Data Systems	8
2.3.3 Collaborative Documents.....	11
2.3.4 Data Transfers	12
2.4 Analysis and conclusions.....	16
<i>3 Summary</i>	17

Table of Figures

Figure 1: EFSS systems and data science environments integrated in ScienceMesh	8
Figure 2: EFSS systems and repositories supported by ScieBRDS.....	10
Figure 3: EFSS systems and authoring applications integrated by the project	11
Figure 4: Data Transfer tools and solutions integrated and piloted by the project	13
Figure 5: Massive datasets transfers amount SURF and PSNC using FTS.....	14

1 Introduction

This document provides an analysis and summary of the work in WP4 of the CS3MESH4EOSC project related to the full validation of the applications and use-cases integrated with EFSS in the context of portability and re-usability of the integrations and solutions worked out.

These application areas include the use-cases and workflows related to the data-based collaboration: Collaborative Data Science, Collaborative Documents Editing, Open Data Systems and FAIR, and managing data migration, replication and placement (Data Transfer).

The focus of this deliverable is the portability of the application software components, re-deployability of the services built using them as well as applicability and re-usability of the application integration models worked out.

Portability of the components, models and integration approaches is one of the key aspects that may influence practical usability and sustainability of the project results within and beyond the environment of sites that initially participated in the project. They may impact the actual adoption of the CS3MESH4EOSC software products and the overall adoption of the federation concept that has been proposed by the project.

The background of this work is discussed in deliverable D4.1: "Demonstration of application functionality across federated shares" providing the overview of the use-cases, application-level building blocks, technical design and integration work and early prototypes. D4.1 summarizes the requirements analysis, the overall architecture design, the developments and integrations as well as the early prototypes of the services available until M18, demonstrated during the mid-term EC review of the project.

The advanced demonstrators are discussed in D4.2. It presents the state of application services components and discusses their integration in M36 which has been set as an important project checkpoint (the project execution has been prolonged by 6 months, until June 2023). D4.2 details the design, integration and implementation work related to particular service areas. It also discusses the user-group-oriented evaluation and testing of the early and advanced pilots and summarises the feedback collected during the validation.

The portability aspect has already been included in the M1-M18 and the M18-M36 work reported in D4.1 and D4.2. However, it deserves special attention and dedicated efforts. Therefore, it is also addressed in the separate deliverable D4.3.

2 Full validation of the use-cases for all workflows

Within WP4 of the CS3MESH4EOSC project, a set of user-level applications has been developed with the aim of being embedded into this federated mesh of sync & share systems. They include Collaborative Data Science environments, Collaborative Document Editing platforms and solutions, Open Data Systems FAIR and Data Transfers mechanisms.

An important milestone of the workplan is the practical validation of portability of the application-level solutions worked out including the application components themselves as well as the model, architecture and implementation of the integration of applications with EFSS systems and with the mesh. While the by-design portability and openness were at the center of the overall project idea, the concept of the federation and the design, architecting, implementation and integration work performed, the focus of this analysis is the practical validation of portability and reusability of applications, EFSS and federations integrations, based on real-life experience.

In the following sections, overall portability considerations are provided along with the detailed analysis of the portability of the solutions in particular application areas.

2.1 Portability considerations

The design, integration and implementation work within WP4 and in the project in general has been conducted with portability in mind from the very beginning.

This is reflected in the designed architecture modularity, use of existing standards wherever possible and clear definition of the interfaces among the logical layers at various levels: application-, federation-, EFSS- and backend storage-level. Also, the interfaces to the external systems (e.g. to repositories) and projects have been standardised as far as possible.

Also, while choosing the building blocks and core technologies, decisions have been made to use widely adopted, default and de-facto standard components. This has applied both to the overall federation design and in particular to the WP4-level applications integration work.

For the Data Science environments, Jupyter Notebooks¹ have been adopted as the core solution (actually JupyterLab v3). ScieboRDS² developed at the University of Münster has been selected as a mature Open Data platform supporting data deposit to de-facto standard repositories: Open Science Framework (OSF) and OpenAIRE-based Zenodo. OnlyOffice and Collabora have been taken for Collaborative Editing platforms, among others due to their support for WOPI, the de-facto standard interface for authoring applications. RClone³ has been used as the tool for performing ad-hoc Data Transfers controlled by end-users, while

¹ <https://jupyter.org/>

² <https://github.com/Sciebo-RDS/Sciebo-RDS>

³ <https://rclone.org/>

FTS and Rucio have been adopted as the massive data transfer tools that are de-facto standard in the large scale European research infrastructures.

2.2 Portability validation

Portability validation applies to the outcomes of the design, architecting, integration and evaluation work conducted for the application-level and user-oriented functionality.

In the first period (M1-M18), this work focused on designing the overall architecture, interfaces and protocols and development of the prototypes of the services along with the prototype federation layer for EFSS systems and applications. These early prototypes were mostly used for internal testing within the sites where the original design and development has been conducted, therefore the analysis of the portability has not been the first priority.

In the second period of the project (M18-M36) the scope of the evaluation of early prototypes has been broadened, targeting at collecting feedback and ensuring that the advanced prototypes, production and pre-production versions of the services can be run also beyond the initial deployments. An aspect of this work was increasing interoperability of the software and services components at all levels: application, EFSS and EFSS federation.

Within this work, it has been proven that the application components and the federation model itself enable interoperation and reusability of the application-, EFSS- and EFSS federation-level solutions. The following points provide a more detailed analysis.

2.3.1 Data Science Environments

Original environments for the Data Science applications in all sites participating in the project have been built around Jupyter Notebooks⁴.

CERN's Data Science platform included SWAN⁵ (Service for Web based ANALysis) that is composed of Jupyter Notebooks combined with dockerized Spark and Hadoop data analytics platforms as well as CERNBox, the OCIS-based EFSS and EOS (CERN's scalable filesystem). The Data Science platform at JRC is the re-deployed SWAN that, in the case of JRC, uses HTCondor for computing and Kubernetes for resource orchestration as well as ownCloud 10 as the EFSS, and EOS. The configuration of SWAN was adapted to JRC's strict security measures. The Data Science platform at PSNC used the vanilla JupyterLab v3, OpenShift and OpenStack for compute resources provisioning and orchestration. The NextCloud-based EFSS uses WebDAV and DAVfs or RClone based storage back-end synchronisation mechanics.

During the course of the project, several extensions of the data science environments have been made. In particular, JupyterLab has been extended towards supporting the ScienceMesh

⁴ <https://jupyter.org/>

⁵ <https://swan.web.cern.ch/swan/>

federation through a CS3API4LAB plugin⁶. The plugin provides access to the federated datasets via the JupyterLab user interface (both GUI and CLI) and interacts with the federation layer in order to perform collaborative editing and notebooks sharing actions.

Project-delivered extensions included also enabling advanced visualisation capabilities for JupyterLab. With Voila, the data analysis workflows created with Jupyter notebooks can be compiled to Voilà dashboards⁷ for broader usage by less experienced users. In addition, the VOIS library⁸ developed by JRC, partially based on the CS3MESH4EOSC project funding extended the data visualisation capabilities even further by providing the end users with the tools for creation of modern dashboards based on packaged reusable components.

Jupyter notebooks at PSNC have been enriched by integrating them with NextCloud so that users of Jupyter's GUI, CLI and kernels spawned by the Jupyter environment can access the same data on the Jupyter and EFSS underlying storage.

These three environments have been developed, extended and integrated with EFSS systems and compute and storage backends and with the federation layer in a coordinated way.

As a result, mutual reusability of the components created has been achieved. For instance, CS3API plugin can be used at PSNC to achieve visibility of data to the Jupyter GUI and CLI and EFSS instead of the EFSS-storage integration based on WebDAV and DAVfs.

It has also been proven that the set of application-level and EFSS federation-level components worked out can be deployed and used with various, heterogeneous implementations of EFSS systems including, OCIS, ownCloud 10 and NextCloud. In addition, on the application level, the solutions are portable and interoperable - this applies to SWAN that includes a tuned version of Jupyter, tightly integrated with other SWAN components as well as vanilla JupyterLab, that is used at PSNC and in other sites participating in the mesh.

Overall, supported by the software deployment mechanics, the solutions worked out within the Data Science related task can be redeployed also to sites other than those already included in the mesh. Relevant deployment configurations - for Docker, Kubernetes and OpenShift have been prepared and tested across four sites: CERN, JRC, PSNC (testing, pre-production and production) and Ailleron (development).

Data Science environments adopted by the project have potential also to integrate new functionality that extends the basic, local data analysis workflows, such as triggering the ad-hoc data transfers through the JupyterLab interface using Rucio⁹. Such capability was

⁶ <https://github.com/sciencemesh/cs3api4lab>

⁷ <https://github.com/voila-dashboards/voila>

⁸ https://vois.readthedocs.io/en/latest/1_intro.html

⁹ <https://rucio.cern.ch>

developed and demonstrated as a 2020 Google Summer of Code project “Making Exabytes of LHC data seamlessly accessible on Jupyter Notebooks”¹⁰.

The summary of the EFSS, data science and compute platforms supported in the ScienceMesh is presented in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1: EFSS systems and data science environments integrated in ScienceMesh

2.3.2 Open Data Systems

The most comprehensive interoperability and reusability validation exercise has been conducted within the Open Data Systems context.

ScieboRDS¹¹ developed at the University of Münster has been the starting point of that work. It was chosen as a mature Open Data platform supporting data deposit to de-facto standard repositories: Open Science Framework (OSF) and OpenAIRE-based Zenodo. It also has an active user base, connected to the Sciebo service¹², that is a large-scale EFSS with 227k users from universities and computing centers across North-Rhine Westfalia (Germany).

ScieboRDS uses standard components and interfaces to large extent. It interfaces with popular EFSS systems and repositories. It also uses RO-Crates¹³, a widely-adopted, specification for packaging of research data sets and accompanying metadata.

ScieboRDS functionality for data sharing, collaborative curation, enrichment, annotation and packaging has been evaluated among others at the University of Münster (WWU) and at the University of Potsdam. This effort was partially funded by CS3MESH4EOSC project.

¹⁰ https://hepsoftwarefoundation.org/gsoc/2020/proposal_SWAN_RUCIO_integration.html

¹¹ <https://github.com/Sciebo-RDS/Sciebo-RDS>

¹² <https://hochschulcloud.nrw/>

¹³ <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/>

The SURF port / deployment (and extensions)

SURF, another CS3MESH4EOSC partner, integrated ScieboRDS with their EFSS service, SURFdrive. The ported service addresses the needs of the Dutch research and education community related to dealing with depositing data sets to repositories, in a systematic way.

Given the common technological basis for the Sciebo and SURFdrive EFSS systems (both are ownCloud 10-based), deploying ScieboRDS for SURFdrive did not pose any major problems or need for modifications on the ScieboRDS system. In addition to the deployment, SURF has developed a number of new connectors for ScieboRDS in order to enable sharing data to other research repositories that are widely used among their user base in the Netherlands including Figshare, iRODS and Dataverse.

This adaptation has been possible thanks to the open architecture of ScieboRDS, composed of an easily expandable set of microservices, as well as the fact that it employs standard components and concepts such as Describo and ROCRATE, the tool and the standard packaging and annotation format that facilitate and systematise the preparation of the research data sets for deposit to open repositories.

The SUNET's modified stack demonstrator

An extended version of the Open Data system based on ScieboRDS has been deployed at SUNET, an early adopter and contributor to the solution, external to the project consortium.

SUNET integrated the ScieboRDS-based Open Data application with their Nextcloud EFSS. The modified solution was deployed as part of SUNET Drive, the SUNET-provided EFSS.

Moreover, SND (Swedish National Data Service) has begun work on a connector for their own data repository, DORIS. The DORIS project run by SUNET is a national infrastructure for the publication of research data. It addresses 2000+ users holding ~300 TBs of data. DORIS has their own system for describing and sharing data in the SND catalogue. Having an RDS connector to DORIS available through SUNET Drive, will enable implementing simplified workflows for scientists. Data can be stored in SUNET Drive and eventually be directly published to the repository in a systematic way, avoiding the manual deposit hassle.

The results of the initiative at SUNET reached the pilot and pre-production phase and are now being exposed to the interested end-users. The full demonstrator has been presented during the dedicated workshop "Science Mesh – Global Platform for Scientific Collaboration"¹⁴ on Jun, the 9th 2023, colocated with TNC23 conference in Tirana, where both the architecture of the solution and functionality has been explained¹⁵.

Moreover, both: the original ScieboRDS at University of Münster and the ported ScieboRDS at SUNET) have been presented during the main programme of the TNC23 conference, within

¹⁴ <https://tnc23.geant.org/programme/?day=Friday%209/6>

¹⁵ https://drive.switch.ch/index.php/s/4qxtFVZw74sgLLW#/files_mediatviewer/03_SCIEBO%20video%20TNC.mp4

dedicated data management-related session “ALL DATA BIG & SMALL”¹⁶ in the presentation “Sciebo RDS - reducing friction of FAIR data handling for researchers”¹⁷.

ScieboRDS as the mature, standard solution for research data management

Sciebo RDS now supports a range of EFSS systems including ownCloud (University of Münster, SURF), and NextCloud (SUNET). It can also support data sets deposits to the most popular repositories: OSF, Zenodo as well as WWU datasafe, FigShare, iRODS and DataVerse.

The summary of the platforms supported by ScieboRDS is presented in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2: EFSS systems and repositories supported by ScieboRDS

Technically, the integration of ScieboRDS with its host EFSS is implemented as a native wrapper plugin around a standalone RDS web application. This enables utilising basic EFSS functionality such as file picker for data objects selection and OAUTH for user management, tapping into the EFSS’s native user management. On the data deposit side, each storage provider or repository interface is implemented as its own microservice. This ensures that: (1) it is relatively straightforward to integrate new plugins for EFSS systems by developing a native plugin for that EFSS; (2) support for new repositories can be added by developing

¹⁶ <https://tnc23.geant.org/sessions/#s254>

¹⁷ https://indico.geant.org/event/2/contributions/141/attachments/137/380/TNC23_ScieboRDS_final.pptx

microservices that implement a simple ScieboRDS API on one side and map to the repository API on the other side.

Overall, the successful deployment of the Open Data services components, initially developed and operated at the University of Münster (WWU), and replanted to two sites and adopted to their requirements and specifics related to the EFSS system to be integrated and repositories to be supported prove that the solution works, adds to the portfolio of ScienceMesh application services, and is portable and reusable across various sites, even those that are based on different EFSS systems and require additional repository integration.

2.3.3 Collaborative Documents

Collaborative Documents editing platforms are among the most popular applications integrated with EFSS systems. Also the integration itself has been the most straightforward when it comes to the architecturing and design decisions. The obvious way was to apply the WOPI protocol, that is the de-facto standard interface for authoring applications. It enabled integrating Collabora at the first run, already before M18. In the latter period it was used to integrate OnlyOffice and other applications including Etherpad and Overleaf. WOPI was also considered to be used to perform the integration of Diagrams.net (Draw.io) and Excalidraw.

The summary of the authoring applications integrated within the project’s timeline and planned for future is presented in Figure 3 below.

Figure 3: EFSS systems and authoring applications integrated by the project

Technically, the WOPI Bridge¹⁸ module was developed by CERN for its CERNBox service and adopted and extended for the purposes of CS3MESH4EOSC. WOPI integration enabled the file updates to be triggered in the storage system (e.g. in EFSS and in federation) in response to notifications received from the online editing application, caught through the hooks to

¹⁸ <https://github.com/cs3org/wopiserver/blob/master/src/bridge/readme.md>

the Web interfaces of the applications. Such a mechanism has been implemented for CodiMD. Similar mechanics are applied while trying the integrations of the other collaborative editing platforms into the mesh.

The development, integration and deployment work conducted with the project confirmed what should be expected if the standard, widely-adopted components are applied. It has been confirmed that the WOPI-based integration of authoring applications work across sites: including the largest installations at CERN (37k users), the University of Münster (237k users) and also in PSNC, SURF, SWITCH, CESNET and others. They also work across technologies of EFSS systems, including OCIS (at CERN), ownCloud 10 (WWU, SURF, SWITCH, CESNET) and NextCloud (PSNC, and the early adopter site SUNET).

2.3.4 Data Transfers

Data Transfer solution integration into EFSS software stack and EFSS federation applied to two use-cases and two relevant types of the tools and services. For small-scale transfers, typically triggered in the ad-hoc way by the human operators, an RClone-based solution has been integrated. This type of data transfers is relevant for individual researchers or research groups. For large-scale managed massive data transfers the more systematic solutions have been applied based on interfacing to Rucio and FTS¹⁹ services. Rucio is a data management tool developed at CERN in order to manage geographically distributed data sets. FTS is a tool which manages the actual data transfers from one site to another (also developed at CERN). Managed data transfers typically involves geographically distributed large scale scientific communities having a federated AAI system.

Standard tools and services

RClone is a general-purpose, universal, Swiss army knife-like data transfer tool with a wide range of data access/storage protocols supported, multi-threading capability and lightweight architecture that enable relatively easy integration, also within the EFSS environment.

FTS (File Transfer Service) and Rucio are recognised and widely accepted services user for massive, managed data transfers in large scientific projects (e.g. WLCG and others). They have been developed initially used in the context of LHC, but over the decade their adoption has been spread across most of the academic sites and projects within Europe.

Data access protocols support

RClone and FTS/Rucio support many types of storage endpoints and protocols. RClone supports a range of popular protocols including object storage (S3), Web: including WebDAV, HTTP and filesystem-like (FTP, SFTP etc.) and public cloud storage such as Dropbox, Google Drive. It may also interface directly with ownCloud, NextCloud and Seafiler. FTS/Rucio supports many types of storage endpoints: WebDAV, HTTPs, GridFTP, xrootd and SRM. Both classes of tools and services have proven to be usable across sites and use-cases. Rclone has been used

¹⁹ <https://cern.ch/fts>

among EFSS sites during the solution development (SURF, CERN, WWU, CESNET and by the external users, including the participants of the pilot from HPC.NRW project²⁰ that involved universities of Münster and Paderborn.

Rucio and FTS has been used internally among project partners sites and in the pilots involving external infrastructures - e.g. tests of massive data sets transfers among SURF - CS3MESH4EOSC project site and the mesh node and the Laboratoire d'Annecy de Physique des Particules (LAPP) - the ESCAPE project partner.

Control CLIs and APIs

RClone can be used as a stand-alone tool through the CLI. It can also run as a service and be communicated through the HTTP API, for triggering and controlling the data transfers. Similarly, FTS provides Python-based CLI and Python client as well as WebFTS portal that can be used to trigger and monitor the data transfer jobs and their state. These control CLI and API can be used for the integration of the tools in the data management services stacks.

Services and tools integration summary

The summary of the data transfer applications and services integrated and piloted withing the project work is presented in Figure 4 below.

Figure 4: Data Transfer tools and solutions integrated and piloted by the project

Deployability

Besides the architectural and technical openness, practical re-usability of the integrated solutions is often impacted by the amount of effort needed to deploy them in sites.

It is quite obvious that usage and deployment of RClone is relatively easy as it is a stand-alone tool runnable on most operating systems and distributed through packages for most standard

²⁰ <https://hpc.dh.nrw/en/>

Linux distributions²¹. On the other hand, the common understanding is that setting up Rucio and FTS involves more overhead and may require specialised knowledge.

However, within one of the pilots, it has been proven that the effort needed to setup the instances of the services such as FTS is moderate and can be minimised by containerisation

Within this pilot a dedicated instance of FTS has been set up in order to conduct the massive radio-astronomy data transfers among the data infrastructures. The data have been transferred among SURF and PSNC, that are LOFAR Long Term Archive (LTA nodes). LTA sites keep PB-scale archival data gathered from stations across Europe, centrally pre-processed in Astron, Groningen, Netherlands and then distributed to the LTA locations in SURF (Netherlands), FZJ (Germany) and PSNC (Poland).

The purpose of this limited-scale pilot was to evaluate how the EFSS platforms can be used to facilitate the data handling in LOFAR. While the pilot reached only the early stage, it involved the testing data transfers among the data infrastructures: the LOFAR LTA site in SURF and the CS3MESH4EOSC testbed at PSNC. The default data management platform for LOFAR is dCache, therefore the data transfer options included GridFTP. FTS could be used in that case in order to trigger and manage the 3-rd party data transport. The overall schema of the testing data transfers performed during the pilot is presented in Figure 5 below.

Figure 5: Massive datasets transfers amount SURF and PSNC using FTS

Notably, the full setup of the FTS server, along with monitoring portal has been completed within several hours, including deploying a dedicated Linux virtual machine, installing the

²¹ <https://rclone.org/downloads/>

software stack including apache, Globus- and FTS-dedicated packages as well as requesting, and installing Grid and SSL certificates for GridFTP client and FTS monitoring tool Web server. The service deployment could be further facilitated by using containerisation for FTS server.

Overall, the experiment proved that setting up the dedicated FTS is not problematic. Rucio, on the other hand, is typically set up for large data infrastructure such as ESCAPE or WLCG by their admins that are familiar with distributed data management software stacks. Therefore, the FTS is the only component of the overall solution that typically needs to be set up as a dedicated instance (due to specific user credentials policies etc.). Setup of FTS should not be the blocker for the wider adoption of the integrated data transfer solution.

2.4 Analysis and conclusions

In the previous points we have analysed the portability and reusability of particular applications as well as application-EFSS and application-mesh integration components.

Data Science applications and integrations have been tested across three sites: CERN, JRC and PSNC, running various software: SWAN, Vanilla Jupyter, Spark, Hadoop, HTC Condor, OpenStack, OpenShift and K8s, EFSSes: OCIS, ownCloud 10 and NextCloud; and storage back-ends: EOS, regular POSIX filesystem etc.

Open Data application has been ported from WWU to SURF and SUNET. It runs integrated with ownCloud 10 and NextCloud EFSS as well as supports plethora of repositories including OSF, Zenodo, Figshare, DataVerse and storage systems interfaces such as iRODS and Reva.

Collaborative Editing applications' integration component (WOPI Bridge) can run virtually everywhere, based on the support of the WOPI protocol in authoring applications including Collabora and OnlyOffice. Also non-obvious application can be successfully integrated and tested across sites including CodiMD, Etherpad (full integration) and Overleaf (pilots).

Data Transfer solution integration proved to be applicable to small-scale ad-hoc RClone-based data transfers for individuals and systematic solutions including Rucio and FTS suitable for cross-infrastructure managed transfers of massive datasets. It also proved to be usable across the sites due to the overall adoption of the technologies such as FTS.

Overall it has been proven, that the application components and the federation itself enable interoperation and reusability the application-, EFSS- and EFSS federation-level solutions.

The reusable components are the building blocks that can be used to provide FAIR-related and data-centric applications across many sites and disciplines. Their reusability and portability can be exploited while extending the mesh beyond the original project consortium, by including new EFSS sites, as well as beyond the initial set of the technical building blocks, including application-level components, EFSS systems and storage systems.

3 Summary

In this report we summarized the work on the validation of portability of the application software components and re-deployability of the services built using them, in two dimensions: (1) porting the service components among heterogeneous EFSS, infrastructure, platform and storage software stacks (2) re-deploying the services in multiple sites. We also analysed and concluded on the overall applicability and re-usability of the application-level functionality developments and the integration models worked out.

Portability is one of the key aspects that may influence the usability and the adoption of the project results as well as their long term sustainability. It also may facilitate spreading the federation across sites, institutions and end-user groups.

The analysis conducted in this document complements the analysis included in D4.1 and D4.2. Those deliverables documented the initial project work (design, integration, early prototyping) and the advanced stage of work (testing the early prototypes, collecting feedback, improving implementation and advancing integration on the prototypes) leading to ready-to-use products or mature prototypes. They can be exposed and presented to the end-user communities and tested on a larger scale beyond the project partners' sites.

Based on our experience, we believe that the federation features of the mesh, both in the horizontal dimension, i.e. the capability to glue multiple sites and technologies together and in the vertical dimension, i.e. the capability to integrate various application stacks, reached the state, where they can organically grow towards new sites and new applications.

Obviously, the evolution requires time and effort to happen on a larger scale, however the work done in the project shows that it is technically and organisationally possible to extend the federation: new sites and new features can be added based on validated EFSS systems and application components, and organised following the mesh concept.

The architectural and organisational openness of the mesh provides yet another incentive for sites, application developers and users to join, benefit from and contribute to the federation. In turn, extending the federation, by involving more and more nodes and users, contributes to strengthening the European academic and research on-premise services base.

These services can be used for establishing the mesh of sites and services that will provide an alternative to the public cloud offerings of large vendors that dominate the European IT services market these days, thus enabling European research and education institutions and individuals to keep the digital sovereignty and stay in control of their valuable datasets.

While reaching these high-level goals requires also acting on the policy, regulatory, legal, funding, education and awareness building level, the FAIR-supportive and data reusability-targeted applications and services developed by the CS3MESH4EOSC project constitute the technical facilitators and contribution to this process.